
**VERBALIZATION OF THE CONCEPT OF "FRIENDSHIP" IN THE
ENGLISH LITERARY TEXTS**

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Annotation The article is about cultural concepts and their verbalization in literary texts. The study of such concepts as "friendship" involves the analysis of those fragments of the text and those phraseological units that are somehow connected with this phenomenon in order to identify the concept of this reality. In order to establish the elements of these concepts, we've referred to the semantic structure of the names associated with this general concept.

Key words: culture, friendship, concept, language, category.

Different types of knowledge are represented in human mind in a form of cognitive and linguistic categories that, as a whole, form global, universal and cultural concepts. Concept as a category is understood as a multidimensional structure in collective mind, having a linguistic realization and representing the primary cultural formation, reflecting national worldview and experience. Concepts are determined by culture and, thus, serve as a mechanism of transmitting culture through generations [1,85]. Concepts accumulate all the information acquired by a nation and a human being individually, and are manifested in meanings of lexical and grammatical units. If so, linguistic means are the reflection of thought, cognition, and, which is more important, culture and cultural values. Meaning then is understood as a definite type of information acquired and processed by means of language.

The above stated speaks for the fact that every language shows national mentality that comprises knowledge, experience, culture and cultural values of particular nation and national identity. The image of the world, formed in human mind in a process of conceptualization and realized by means of language, is often referred to as “the linguistic representation (picture) of the world” [2,61]. The latter is always culturally unique as every society perceives the world through the prism of its culture.

The analysis of cultural concepts serves also as a key to understanding national prototypical models of peoples' behavior in different situations that are often culturally and socially based. These models reflect the cultural “rules” and values of a nation [3, 90]. In the history of any national culture, issues relating to human relationships, such as love and friendship, have always been and still are of paramount importance. People are trying to figure out what is the meaning of friendship, who is a friend, and why friendship is so necessary, but these eternal

questions, which have no unambiguous interpretation, cause much controversy. Nevertheless, mankind does not leave persistent attempts to comprehend the phenomenon of friendship itself; self-awareness, the perception of life and the worldview of humanity is largely determined by the attitude to friendship.

The study of such concepts as "friendship" involves the analysis of those fragments of the text and those phraseological units that are somehow connected with this phenomenon in order to identify the concept of this reality. In order to establish the elements of these concepts, it is necessary, first of all, to refer to the semantic structure of the names associated with this general concept. Roge's thesaurus allows to determine the range of actively used tokens in connection with the concept of "friendship". In the first place there are agreement, compatibility, understanding, ability to form groups, common interests, intimate, sexual and family relationships, sponsorship, love, the beginning and restoration of friendship.

From these meanings, it can be concluded that the main point of friendship is communication with a person, based on mutual similarity, knowledge of the qualities of this person and love, which brings peace and tranquility; it has a beginning, can be interrupted and then resumed. A friend is opposed to the enemy.

Based on the results of the study of the Roge's thesaurus, the interpretation of the concept will be carried out by considering the elements that can be distinguished using the most actively used tokens:

- Friendship – Amity; Friendship – Sociality; Friendship – Brotherhood; Friendship – Likeness; Friendship – Knowledge; Friendship – Love; Friendship – Intimacy; Friendship – Support.

It is possible that in the process of research work other elements will be highlighted that make up the concept of "friendship". First of all we'll investigate Friendship - Peace Relations ("Amity"), how they are verbalized in literary texts.

Friends bring peace to our lives, we feel not alone and protected. The ability to speak out to someone, the ability to share with someone the pleasure of joint action calms. Not by chance, a friend is called a cure:

«A faithful friend is the medicine of life» “The Bible”.

The cordiality of the relationship, mutual pleasure make friendship one of the best human relationships. Friendship is not only a duty, but also a pleasure:

"Friendship is not always the sequel of obligation" (Samuel Johnson).

Having a friend in our life gives us some confidence that all sorrows will pass. In anger, you can speak to a loved one, and the anger will calm down:

“I was angry with my friend;

I told my wrath, my wrath did end.

I was angry with my foe:

It told me not my wrath did grow ”(William Blake).

Friends have nothing to divide among themselves, and therefore a conflict situation can not arise: "Between friends all is common" (proverb)

It's pleasant to make various minor things with friends, and from the fact that they are close to each other, these actions become more pleasant:

«And the whole summer, when you drive around in the car with your friends, you see the corn grow» (Bushnell, 2002:115).

Then much has already been achieved and there is no need to strive anywhere, the faithful friend becomes an integral part of our existence, with him we want to spend time in peace.

Next our investigation is Friendship - communication ("Sociality").

Friendly communication in all ages has a high moral and psychological value, the presence of friends is considered one of the most important prerequisites of psychological comfort and satisfaction with life. The possibility of companionship makes our life "hopeless":

"Hopeless hope hopes and meets no end,

Wastes without springs and homes without a friend "(John Clare).

Friendly communication involves not only discussing some problems, but also the sincerity of opinions and attitudes:

«There is no man so friendless but what he can find a friend sincere enough to tell him disagreeable truths» (Edward George Bulwer Lytton).

Friends are something close and necessary in our lives. And the fact that they give news is not so important, how much they give us confidence that we are not alone:

«If he was lucky, there would also be owls carrying letters from his best friends Ron and Hermione, though any expectation he'd had that their letters would bring him news had long since been dashed» (Rowling, 2003: 3).

Sharing our problems and experiences in friendly communication, we spend a lot of time with our friends, and this is not always a positive thing: "Friends are thieves of time," says an English proverb.

High social mobility, frequent changes of residence, work, etc., undermine the stability of personal relationships and affections, make them short-term, unreliable and ephemeral. Attitudes of people with each other are becoming increasingly temporary, non-permanent. People, as well as things and places, pass through our life, without stopping, at an accelerated pace. Most often we enter into superficial, business relationships with people around us. Consciously or not, we build our relationships with most people on a functional basis. And companionship loses its sincerity, a friend acquires the status of just an interlocutor, with whom, as with a casual acquaintance, you can spend several hours of our life, just talking:

"And even now, at twenty-five,

He has to keep alive!

Yes! All day long from 10 till 4!

For half the year or even more;

With one hour or two

At luncheon with a city friend ” (Hillaire Belloc).

“I have no problems. No fear of disease, psychopaths, or stalkers. “Why not just be with your friends and have real conversations and a good time?” (Bushnell, 2002: 5)

The personal presence of a friend is no longer required, we can talk on the phone or via the Internet:

«'Anyway, we're not lonely. We have extended families in the form of networks of friends connected by telephone,' said Tom» (Fielding, 1999: 64).

Probably, the tone of sincerity of friendship and the need for friendship is preserved in the terms “good friends” and “great friends”: the definition of “great” gives a new shade to the concept of “friend”, characterizing a friend as a wonderful, great person:

«“Please, darling,” Bunny said. “Men like Jingles, and there’s a whole group of them in New York, are not the type of guys you marry. They make great friends – attentive, always there, when you are in a tight spot – and late at night when you’re lonely and desperate as hell, you whisper to yourself”» (Bushnell, 2002:191).

« If you are writing to Mother at any point, you might tell her that a certain Sturgis Podmore, who is a great friend of Dumbledore's, has recently been sent to Azkaban for trespass at the Ministry» (Rowling, 2003: 114).

Often the noun “friend” is accompanied by the adjective “good” in various degrees of comparison to reinforce the meaning of the word “friend” itself, informing the information that this person is a good friend, which distinguishes him from other friends. Thus, in precedent texts we see the expression 1) “good friend”:

«I am very much looking forward to getting to know you all and I'm sure we'll be very good friends!» (Rowling, 2003: 81)

«Start to wonder whether am really good friend. We are all so selfish and busy in London. Would it be possible for one of my friends to be so unhappy that they... ooh, that's where I put this month's Marie Claire: on top of fridge!» (Fielding, 1999: 84)

«“Of course, we are still really good friends,” he added. “We see each other all the time. We just don’t have sex.”» (Bushnell, 2002:9);

2) «better friends»:

«How come we are not better friends?” Ray asked.» (Bushnell, 2002:56);

3) «best friends»:

Using the superlative degree of the adjective “good”, the author distinguishes his friend from among other, even good friends, implying that this friend is the best:

«Getting a married man. I would never be able to pull it off. I’d probably end up becoming best friends with his wife» (Bushnell, 2002:84).

«Other people say you are a bitch, but I say, “No, she is one of my best friends and she is not like that.” I defend you» (Bushnell, 2002:127).

«Caroline and Cici are best friends through the usual conduit of bounding female friendship in New York: Over some jerky guy» (Bushnell, 2002:128).

Sometimes a strong expression “best friend” is intentionally enhanced by the author:

«Was he, Harry, Ron's best friend in the world, going to sulk because he didn't have a badge, laugh with the twins behind Ron's back, ruin this for Ron when, for the first time, he had beaten Harry at something?» (Rowling, 2003: 64)

«'Look,' he said, 'your father was the best friend I ever had and he was a good person. A lot of people are idiots at the age of fifteen. He grew out of it'» (Rowling, 2003: 256).

Summarizing, we can say that friendly communication is necessary for us, but it has lost a shade of sincerity, having acquired, at the same time, the meaning of plurality and distance. In order to emphasize the sincerity of feelings, the need for a friend in life, the terms “good friends” and “great friends” are used.

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